

DESIGN OF SMART WEARABLE DEVICE FOR EFFECTIVE MONITORING OF HEALTH VITAL SIGNS

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ABSTRACT

Early detection and diagnosis of basic health conditions could lead to successful treatment and reduced fatality rate in developing countries, as it is possible to extract human bio-signals and use it to better understand the bodily health status and reaction to external factors. This new Vital Smart System (VSS) design have in-built sensors which a user wears as a wrist band without interfering with his/her daily life activities to monitor his/her major vital signs (BT, BP, HR), of which current system have limitations to achieve. Using the Dynamic System Design Methodology (DSDM), a more technically robust, cost-effective and portable real time device was designed. This device will have an IoT interface (BLE) to connect to smart phones; a GSM interface (SIM900A) relying on AT command framework to access defined medical personnel on the network in cases of emergencies; optical health LEDs to alert the user; thus, enabling consistent self-assessment of an individual's health condition. This work is a quest to provide a generalized smart three-in-one vital sign system to improve the monitoring and reporting of user's health status through optimizing the offline and online cross-interfaces of standalone sensors in line with the country network and health delivery system.

Keywords: Real-time monitoring, Temperature (BT), IoT, Vital Signs, Wearable Heath Device.

INTRODUCTION

Vital signs *are* the different crucial physiological/medical signs that can be measured; to indicate the status of the body's vital functions. It is possible to extract human bio-signals and use it to better understand the bodily health status and reaction to external factors (Dias, Cunha. 2019). Early detection and diagnosis of basic health conditions could lead to successful treatment and reduced fatality rate in developing countries, as many illnesses and diseases can be diagnosed early and hence treated before it becomes fatal. For example, heart attack, which is believed to be instantaneous gives signs, symptoms, to the sufferer but because the signs are not identified and responded to, the illness gets to the stage where it simply knocks down the sufferer. Hence observing the human vital signs are necessary. There are five traditional vital signs that have a major importance to be measured: heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, blood oxygen saturation and body temperature. These five signals are generally considered essential to evaluate human health and a continuous monitoring should be made, especially in patients (Dias & Cunha, 2019).

Mainetti, Patrono & Vilei (2021) identified many wearable medical monitoring systems for vital sign, but a good number of the identified systems measured mostly one vital sign. Thus, this research dwells on developing a device to monitor three of the major five vital signs (of which others are relative to). The basic three vital sign which manifests in various health issues include Blood Pressure, Heart Rate and Body Temperature.

According to Szymański, Chaczko, Rodański (2022) a wearable health device (WHD) is an emerging technology that enables continuous ambulatory monitoring of human vital signs during daily life (during work, at home, during sport activities, etc.) as well as within a clinical environment, with the advantage of minimizing discomfort and interference with normal human activities. WHD have in-built sensors which a user wears without interfering with his/her daily life activities. The wearable devices may be in the form of cloths, wrist bands, shin tights etc. Sensors or actuators have been successfully connected to many physical devices in the past to gather a huge amount of information. According to Farago, et al (2018) for instance, such technology has enabled the development of miniature wearable biomedical devices for certain ubiquitous patient monitoring. It is now straightforward to monitor a series of vital signs, which could enable self-assessment of an individual's health condition.

Problem Statement

Based on the review of literature and the pilot analysis carried out in this work, the existing standalone single vital sign measurement apparatus, though 80% accurate, is 60% deficient, in the efficient and consistent real-time monitoring of users vital signs, therefore showing a research gap to be bridged in this work; by hybridizing and optimizing the impact of these standalone apparatus to design an inexpensive, easy to read/use, real-time hybrid (three-in-one) smart vital sign monitoring device.

Objectives

Our primary objective in this research work is to design a Smart Wearable Devices for easy Monitoring of Health Vital Signs. Specific objectives are to:

- i. Review and analyze existing Vital Health Signs Monitoring systems
- ii. Design the logical and physical input-output modules for the new system using UML.
- iii. Construct the IoT-based network for vital signs transmission.

Research Questions

This study will seek to answer the following research questions:

- i. Does analysis of existing system's deficiencies necessitate design of a new smart wearable device for the vital sign monitoring?
- ii. To what extent can a smart vital sign system input-output module be modelled using UML?
- iii. Can a new IoT-based mobile vital sign transmission system be constructed using specific tools?

Significance of Study

This work is a quest to provide a generalized smart three-in-one vital sign system to improve the monitoring and management of user's health status through optimizing the offline and online cross-interfaces of standalone sensors in line with the country network and health delivery system. As the saying goes, health is wealth, it is hoped that deploying the new smart system for vital sign monitoring would improve the management of individual's health status, thus reducing ill-health and death.

Furthermore, using the system would ensure optimum real time monitoring of vital signs and increased health consciousness of the Nigerian citizens despite the harsh economy. Finally, findings from this study will contribute to the existing literature on the subject area and to the body of knowledge.

Summary of Literature Review

This work reviewed the conceptual, theoretical, and empirical frameworks for achieving the system design and analysis. Table 1.1 presents the summary of the reviewed existing work and their inherent difference from the proposed system.

Table 1.1: Summary of Latest Related Existing Work Reviewed

S/N	Reviewed Work	Apparatus Developed	Technique Involved
1	Nair et al. (2019)	Developed a Vital Sign Monitor to measure ECG, HR, RR.	Big Apparatus, Sends Traffic to PCs, Uses BR/EDR
2	Ali et al. (2020)	Designed and implemented a smart e-Health system. (that is small and wearable- monitoring HR, BM)	Designed a wearable WHD, No Expert System, Uses http as IoT protocol.
3	Lousado et al. (2020)	Developed a device for near real-time monitoring and follow up of elderly and their health condition. (BP, BM)	Uses LoRa as IoT technique
4	Shubham et al. (2018)	Developed an Automated System to measure Vital Signs (BP, HR, BT)	Implemented on Raspberry Pi, Big Device, Emergency Alert Sections

Abbreviations: BM-Body Movement, HR- Heart Rate, BT- Body Temperature, BP- Blood Pressure, WHD -Wearable Health Device, ECG – Electrocardiography.

Samples of Feedback Record from different Smart Watch Vital Sign Monitors

Figure 1.1: Samples of some feedback records from Apple S6 and Samsung galaxy2 vital monitor.

Research Gap:

The empirical review of literature in this work showed the following research needs to explore and which the proposed intelligent system model seems to fix:

1. The absence inexpensive, comfortable, real-time vital sign monitoring wearable device.
2. The absence of SMS notification to the patient's doctor if his/her health begins to deteriorate as determined by the readings of the vital sign.
3. The absence of coloured LED indicators (instead of sound, to ensure user privacy) to notify the patient of his/her health status.

Survey Analyses of Existing Systems

Literature review showed varying implementation of these parameters such as multiple vital sign measurement, computational accuracy, real-time monitoring, cost effectiveness, result interpretation for medical recommendations, data storage for historical use, ease of use/read, processing speed. For each of the parameter listed above, the devices are given a score card on a

0-100% basis. The table 1.2 and figure 1.2 below summarizes the existing reviewed-devices performance.

Table 1.2: Parametric Score of Existing Systems

S/no	Parameter	Score (%)
1	Multiple vital sign measurement	50
2	Computational Accuracy	90
3	Real-time Monitoring	40
4	Cost Effectiveness	40
5	Data storage for historical use	30
6	Ease of Use/Read	70
7	Processing Speed	60
8	Result Interpretation	30
9	Device Adaptability	60

Figure 1.2: Performance Parameters of Existing Systems

Input-Output Design

The embedded wearable device for vital sign sensing comprises of the temperature sensor LM35, and the piezo-electric sensor HK-2000B, the ADS1015 12bit ADC, the AVR328 microcontroller, LCD, LEDs, GSM module, Bluetooth module, Li-ion battery for power supply etc. These are the major components used to design the hardware following the modular method.

Classic Modular Design Method

Here the individual hardware functionality to be designed is represented as a module. Electronic components are then used to satisfy the requirements of the module. The modules of this hardware are temperature sensing module – used to measure the body temperature; pressure sensing module – used to measure the blood pressure; ADC module – used to provide increased resolution for the voltage being measured; processing module – used to process the voltage gotten from the measurement and convert the voltage to the physical parameter value (data), package the data for display and interconnectivity; display module – used to display information; optical indicator module – used to give optical indication of the health status of the patient; GSM module – used to connect to the GSM network in other to send SMS etc; Bluetooth module – used to connect the

wearable device to a smart phone; and buttons module – used to provide user input to the wearable device. These modules are connected following the classic modular block diagram in figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Classic Modular Design of proposed System

All the components making up the embedded wearable device are put together to achieve different functionalities of the modules required for the system to become effective. These components are depicted in the system block diagram in the figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4 The High-Level System Block Diagram

Algorithm Statement for the Wearable Device

- 1) *Setup the ADC module*
- 2) *Setup the serial port for Bluetooth transmission*
- 3) *Setup the GSM module for SMS messaging*
- 4) *Take measurements using temperature sensor and pressure sensor*
- 5) *Update LCD with measured data*
- 6) *Update LEDs with status information*
- 7) *Transmit the vital sign data*
- 8) *Send SMS to medical personnel*

The above algorithm statements were followed to design the proposed hardware system flowchart, dataflows, use-case and activity models encapsulating the system logics, behavior and structure of the proposed system hardware modules.

Logical Design

The proposed system comprises of a wearable vital sign device to measure body temperature, heart rate and blood pressure; hence sensors will be used to achieve this purpose. AVR328p microcontroller is at the core of this wearable device having an analogue to digital converter for data transfer from the sensors. The device will have a SIM900A GSM module, using the AT command framework to communicate with the microcontroller and the GSM network in order to get data to a remote doctor. There will equally be an optical health status indication – using coloured lights to give a health status indicator for the outpatient. The collected vital sign data shall be transmitted to an android app running machine learning optimization algorithm for health analyses and medical recommendation. This IoT interface shall be implemented with BLE as its RF backbone.

The Structured System Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM) Data Flow Model shows the relation between the physical entities of the proposed system, the logical flow of signal and messages between them. The Arrow heads shows the direction of the flow. In each entity is housed the signals/messages it sends and responses it receives throughout the communication circle. The model also shows the involvement of each entity, such that its relevance and dependencies are manifested. The model is pictorially shown in figure 1.5.

Figure 1.5: Dataflow Model of the proposed System

Figure 1.6: Behavioral Use Case Model Diagram

Device Structural Design

In figure 1.7, the VIS input-output activity design model diagram showing the activities of the module parameters and characteristics of how the wearable respective subsystems.

Figure 1.7: Activity Diagram for the Wearable Device

System Firmware

The telemedicine wearable device has the Atmel328P as its core processing chip. This chip has a firmware written using C++ programming language in the Arduino IDE. The operation of the telemedicine wearable device was represented as functionalities; the program written was meant to implement the functionalities as required for the telemedicine wearable device to operate in order to achieve some of the project objectives. The written code follows an algorithm which implements the functionalities that include –

- i. To setup the Atmel328P pins for relevant IO operation
- ii. To setup the ADS1015 ADC module
- iii. To setup the Bluetooth module for RF communication
- iv. To setup the GSM module
- v. To take sensor(s) reading using the ADS1015 ADC module
- vi. To extract and compute relevant data from the readings
- vii. To transfer data to LCD for update
- viii. To transmit data serially using the serial port
- ix. To respond to user requests using the buttons

The VIS Architecture

First a wearable device is developed which can measure the biometric parameters such as blood pressure, heart rate and body temperature. These sensors and measurements are managed by a microcontroller. The microcontroller ensures power management of the device and optimizations during measurement. It equally packages the measured data in a secure format and interfaces with a Bluetooth Low Energy, BLE, based IoT interface. (Mamdiwar et al. 2021) notes that for BLE based IoT interface data security can be enhanced and it consumes very little power. This wearable device will be worn on the wrist.

The Wearable Wrist Device will measure the Vital signs and send SMS to the Patient's Doctor, if vital sign reading indicates the patient's health is beginning to deteriorate. It equally gives optical alerts using colored light on the health status of the patient. Figure 1.8 below shows the Wearable Device (VIS) Architecture.

Figure 1.8: The Smart VIS Wearable Device

Discussion of Findings

The aim of this research exercise is to design a real-time, cost-effective remote vital sign monitoring device for management of user's health status. It is an attempt to add value into our society by creating a model for the development of a three-in-one wrist wearable vital sign monitor, that is easy and comfortable to always wear/read, easily alert the user and his/her personal health care assistance on emergencies, in other words, reducing the rate of infirmity and sudden death in our society. The system designed has proved functional and very effective in achieving the set goals and objectives. This service can be made available to the users by developing and deploying the system to users to serve as a Vital sign Smart System (VSS),

Conclusion and Recommendation

Health is wealth and wellness is best appreciated by a sick person. This system has been designed to detect the vital signs of the body, to indicate the state of health of an individual, is an advantage in preventing sickness and death, giving a model for the development of a device that can be worn on the wrist, like a wrist band for:

- i. a 3-in-1 major vital sign monitor, that is comfortable and easy to use/read

- ii. inexpensive, long-term low power consumption remote observation, management and reporting to users and their personal doctors

This work aids at controlling/reducing the unexpected/sudden high ill-health or death rate that is commonly caused by certain diseases like high blood pressure, heart attack, angina, stroke, atherosclerosis etc; and enable people to remain strong and healthy always. This work has provided a platform for further studies in deploying the above model in the development of a smart wearable vital sign monitoring, management and increasing the health consciousness of users especially in developing countries.

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